

Magnetic nanoparticle tuning for active biosensing performance

A. Makridis¹, K. Kazeli¹, G. Katsipis², E. Tzekaki², A. Pantazaki², M. Angelakeris¹

¹ *Magnetic Nanostructure Characterization: Technology & Applications, Centre for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University, 57001, Thessaloniki, Greece*

² *Laboratory of Neurodegenerative Diseases, Centre for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Aristotle University, 57001, Thessaloniki, Greece*

Email address of the presenting author: agelaker@auth.gr

Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) typically range in size from 1 to 100 nanometers and have unique magnetic properties due to their small size and high surface-to-volume ratio. They are widely exploited as biomedical probes in Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) as contrast agents to enhance imaging, in Drug Delivery where they are guided to specific sites using external magnets, in Hyperthermia Treatment to deliver specific localized heating to kill cancer cells and in Biosensors and Diagnostics to detect biomolecules via magnetic labelling or to magnetically sort of cells or biomolecules. Their facile remote manipulation via magnetic fields together the non-invasive guidance and retrieval and the easily modified surfaces for targeting are key aspects of their exploitation. Yet, challenges to be addressed are aggregation in solution, potential cytotoxicity depending on composition and long-term biocompatibility and clearance from the body. To perform as active biosensing elements, MNPs, should be incorporated to bio-platforms whereby functionalized surfaces and interfaces on them, provide biorecognition support assist by selective binding of DNA, proteins, or cells.

Alzheimer's disease (AD) ranks among the leading causes of adult death standing as the most debilitating form of dementia. Although, its precise onset remains uncertain, underlying pathological changes may appear at preliminary stages many years before clinical cognitive symptoms. Thus, the facile, reliable, specific and sensitive detection of diverse AD biomarkers. Such a multifunctional nanoplatform holds promise for next-generation point-of-care diagnostics and magnetically modulated therapeutic strategies.) is of the essence. In this framework, we evaluate the immobilization of Alzheimer's-specific aptamers on core-shell ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4\text{-Au}$) MNPs surface to selectively capture key biomarkers ($\text{A}\beta_{40}$, $\text{A}\beta_{42}$, p-Tau), enabling rapid and low limits of detection (LOD) across disease stages. Their output is highlighted in high sensitivity to detect trace amounts of biomarkers, rapid detection for fast readout times and suitability for point-of-care (POC) diagnostics, multiplexing allowing for multiple targets detection in parallel and quantitative results enabling precise concentration measurements in a compact biosensor able to detect magnetic field changes linked to target analyte binding.

This work is supported by the European Union under GA No. 101120706 – project 2D-BioPAD.